

Participant Consent

Thank you for participating in this survey.

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Purpose and Objectives of the Research: The purpose of this survey is to better understand the profession of research development in Canada: who we are, what we do, and where we work.

Procedures: If you agree to participate in this survey, you will be asked to complete questions involving basic demographic information as well as information about your institution and your job activities. The survey should take about 15 minutes to complete.

Funded by: This project is funded with professional development funds.

Potential Risks: There are no known or anticipated risks to you by participating in this research.

Potential Benefits: There may not be any direct benefits to you. It is hoped that the information gained from this study can be used to provide an evidence base for understanding how research development is practiced and its strategic role enhancing research competitiveness in the Canadian research ecosystem. However, these benefits are not guaranteed.

Compensation: You will have an opportunity at the end of the survey to enter your work e-mail for a chance to receive a \$5 Tim Hortons or Starbucks gift card for being one of the first 200 respondents to complete the survey. Please note that by entering your work email address, you are providing information that may potentially identify you. However, your work email address is not connected to your survey responses. It is collected in a separate survey.

Confidentiality: Data will be disseminated through conference presentations, webinars, and publications. The data will be reported anonymously in an aggregated/summarized form to ensure that no identifiable information is possible. Any identifying settings in the survey tool will be disabled. The survey is hosted by SurveyMonkey, with data being stored in facilities in Canada. Please see the following for more information on Survey Monkey's [Privacy Policy](#).

Storage of Data: The electronic de-identified data will be stored on a password-protected computer during analyses and moved to a USask system for long-term storage for five years post-publication. When the data is no longer required and following the required storage period, the data will be appropriately erased and destroyed beyond recovery.

Right to Withdraw: Participation in this survey is voluntary. You can decide not to participate at any time by closing your browser. Since the survey is anonymous, once it is submitted it cannot be removed.

Follow-up: To obtain a summary of the results, please contact the principal investigators.

Questions or Concerns: Contact one of the researchers using the contact information listed above. This research project has been approved on ethical grounds by the University of Saskatchewan Behavioural Research Ethics Board. Any questions regarding your rights as a participant may be addressed to that committee through the Research Ethics Office: ethics.office@usask.ca; toll free 1-888-966-2975.

By completing and submitting this questionnaire, your free and informed consent is implied and indicates that you understand the above conditions.

Section 1. Demographic Information

* 1. What are your preferred pronouns at work?

- she/her
- he/his
- they/their
- Other (please specify)

* 2. Select your age range:

- 19 or less
- 20-29
- 30-39
- 40-49
- 50-59
- 60 or more

* 3. What is your highest education level completed?

- College diploma
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree
- Postdoctoral position
- Other (please specify)

* 4. Do you identify as a person belonging to an underrepresented group?

- Visible minority or racialized group
- Indigenous Peoples
- Person with a disability
- Member of the 2SLGBTQIA+ community
- I do not identify as such.
- Other (please specify)

* 5. What language(s) do you use at work?

	Main language	Second language
English	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
French	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Other languages used at work (please specify)

* 6. How many years of work experience do you have in Research Development?

* 7. How many positions have you held in Research Development?

* 8. How many institutions have you worked for in Research Development?

* 9. Which hierarchical level most closely reflects your job in Research Development?

- Senior Leadership
- Director
- Associate or Assistant Director
- Manager
- Staff (e.g. Facilitator, Specialist, Coordinator)
- Research personnel
- Consultant (external to a research institution)
- Other (please specify)

10. What is your job title? (optional)

Section 2. Institutional information

* 11. Where is your institution located?

12. Name of your institution (optional):

* 13. Which description best identifies your institution?

- Community or technical college / CEGEP
- Specialized Institute (e.g. a health research center)
- Primarily undergraduate university
- Comprehensive research university (ACCRU members)
- Medical-doctoral research university (e.g. U15)
- Consulting service (e.g. grant editing, coaching)
- Other (please specify)

* 14. How many Research Development professionals work at your institution?

* 15. What model(s) of Research Development exist at your institution? (check all that apply)

- Central Research office (e.g. with a mix of research administration and research development staff)
- Central Research Development office (e.g. for large, institutional or strategic initiatives)
- Unit-level Research Development (e.g. decentralized in colleges or departments)
- Lab-level Research Development (e.g. in research groups)
- Other (please specify)

* 16. In which Research Development model do you work in?

- Central Research office
- Central Research Development office
- Unit-level Research Development
- Lab-level Research Development
- Other (please specify)

* 17. In a typical year, how many researchers call on your Research Development services (i.e. you as an individual, or a typical staff member in the office you manage)?

- Less than 50
- 50 - 100
- 100 - 200
- More than 200

* 18. Which Research Development services does your institution offer? (check all that apply)

- Grant development support to researchers (general)
- Grant development support specifically for large, institutional or strategic initiatives (e.g. CFI, CRC, SSHRC Partnership)
- Grant workshops and information sessions
- Finding and communicating funding opportunities (listserv, newsletter)
- Internal peer-review programs (e.g. for Tri-Agency funding applications)
- Tri-Agency faculty representatives (e.g. CIHR University Delegates, NSERC and SSHRC Leaders)
- Successful grants repository
- Internal funding programs (e.g. seed or bridge funding)
- Regular networking or information-sharing meetings for research development professionals (e.g. monthly forum)
- Awards facilitation
- Research communications
- Knowledge mobilization services
- Research strategic planning
- Research analytics for insights into research activity
- Postdoctoral fellow support program
- Graduate student support program
- Undergraduate research support program
- Medical resident research support program
- Faculty mentorship
- International research facilitation
- Indigenous research facilitation
- Other (please specify)

Section 3. Job Profile

Please identify your responsibilities in these 5 areas of Research Development (check all that apply).

Note. These are not exhaustive lists, please kindly list other responsibilities we've missed.

* 19. In the area of GRANT DEVELOPMENT:

- Editing and providing feedback
- Writing of non-scientific content (e.g. summary, KT section)
- Writing of scientific content
- Develop budgets and budget justifications
- Troubleshoot with funding agencies
- Project management and team coordination during the proposal development process
- Draft or coordinate letters of support
- Reviewing CVs
- Suggest potential co-investigators or collaborators
- Advise on cash and in-kind contributions
- Review for aspects related to institutional compliance
- Submission support (e.g. navigating sponsor portals)
- Analyse reviewer feedback with unsuccessful applicants
- I do not work in this area.
- Other (please specify)

* 20. What type of grant do you mostly support?

- Natural sciences and engineering
- Health sciences
- Social sciences, arts and humanities
- International grants
- Institutional grants
- All types, no specialization
- I do not support grant development.
- Other (please specify)

*** 21. In the area of RESEARCH COMMUNICATIONS:**

- Communicate and celebrate awards and funding success
- Find and communicate funding opportunities
- Conduct grant workshops and information sessions
- Write or promote research success stories
- Create or update researcher profiles and websites
- Support knowledge mobilization activities (e.g. symposium)
- Develop research marketing products (e.g. external reports, magazines)
- Report on research performance and activity
- I do not work in this area.
- Other (please specify)

*** 22. In the area of RESEARCH COLLABORATION:**

- Facilitate introductions and research connections between researchers
- Convene and coordinate interest groups and multi-disciplinary gatherings
- Develop strategies, databases, and tools that promote collaboration
- I do not work in this area.
- Other (please specify)

*** 23. In the area of DEVELOPMENT of RESEARCHERS:**

- Professional development support to postdoctoral fellows, graduate students, and undergraduate researchers
- Mentorship support to early career researchers or other stages
- Research training support of new research skills (e.g. writing, research methods)
- Inform researchers on emerging research-related issues (e.g. EDI, research security)
- Develop career award nominations
- Promote career advancement opportunities (e.g. CIHR observer program)
- I do not work in this area.
- Other (please specify)

* 28. In your opinion, how effective are Research Development services at your institution?

How could they be improved? (optional)

Thank you for participating in this study!

By clicking Done you will be redirected to an external page (to preserve your anonymity) where you can enter your email to receive a \$5 Tim Hortons or Starbucks gift card. (Limited to the first 200 participants)